

**17th Central European Lung Cancer Conference
including
Best of WCLC 2018**

November 30th 2018 - December 2nd, 2018
Hotel Sheraton, Novi Sad, Serbia

Publisher: Institute for Pulmonary Diseases in Sremska Kamenica and Central European
Lung Cancer Association – CELCA

For Publisher: Prof. Dr Ilija Andrijević, Director

Editor: Prof. dr Ilija Andrijević

Design:

ARIA IT SOLUTIONS

ISBN 978-86-82781-15-8

Dear colleagues,

It is our pleasure to welcome you to the 17th Central European Lung Cancer Conference including Best of WCLC 2018. The Conference is organized by Institute for Pulmonary Diseases in Sremska Kamenica and Central European Lung Cancer Association – CELCA.

The aim of CELCC is to develop strategies for decreasing the burden of lung cancer in Europe. Therefore, we invite different specialists working in the field of lung cancer to participate at the CELCC 2018.

Thank you for your highly appreciated contribution to this Conference.

We wish you a pleasant and rewarding stay in Novi Sad!

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, sincerely,

Prof. Dr Ilija Andrijević
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Prof. Dr Robert Pirker
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IS ANEMIA DURING CHEMOTHERAPY PROGNOSTIC FACTOR FOR PATIENTS WITH NON-SMALL CELL LUNG CANCER?

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Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) is the most common type of lung cancer, and it accounts about 85% to 90% of all lung cancer cases.

The aim of this study was to determine the influence of anemia during chemotherapy as a prognostic factor in patients with non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC).

This was a retrospective-prospective study in which we analyzed 200 patients with NSCLC, stages III and IV, who were treated with chemotherapy (HT) protocols gemcitabin/ cisplatin, and cisplatin/etoposide, (100 patients each protocol). In retrospective period we analyzed hematologic toxicity, and in prospective period which lasted for two years we evaluated survival. In both groups of patients, the experimental group consisted of patients with hematologic toxicity, and the control group was created of patients without hematologic toxicity.

There were no differences in all grades of anemia during chemotherapy between the groups ($p>0.05$). There was no statistically significant difference between the reduced initial values of hemoglobin and the development of anemia all grades, (2, 3 and 4), during treatment with chemotherapy in both groups ($p=0.155$, $p=0.123$, $p<0.05$ for group A and $p=0.103$, $p=0.308$, $p<0.05$ for the group B). Anemia is identified as a prognostic factor in both group of patients using univariate statistical analysis (group A $p<0.025$, group B $p<0.000$), but none of the analyzed parameters did not show statistical significance in the multivariate analysis (in group A $p>0.857$, $p>0.808$, $p>0.683$, and in group B $p>0.233$, $p>0.068$ and $p>0.149$). There was a statistically significant difference in survival of patients in both groups – in group A (Long rank test, $\chi^2=7.708$; $p<0.01$), and in group B (Long rank test, $\chi^2=16.434$; $p<0.01$) (gradus 0, 1 i 2). There was a statistically significant difference in survival of patients in both groups – in group A (Long rank test, $\chi^2=16.434$; $p<0.01$) and in group B (Long rank test, $\chi^2=20.897$; $p<0.01$). (gradus 0, 3 i 4).

In conclusion we can say that statistical analysis confirmed that anemia during chemotherapy is prognostic factor in both groups, but it is not independent prognostic factor.

Key words: anemia, chemotherapy, NSCLC, prognostic factor

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